

ENHANCING ENGAGEMENT OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH THE UTILIZATION OF GAME (GAMES-BASED APPROACHES TO MOTIVATE ENGAGEMENT) INTERVENTION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 2

Pages: 174-184

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2149

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13270446

Manuscript Accepted: 07-01-2024

Enhancing Engagement of High School Students through the Utilization of GAME (Games-Based Approaches to Motivate Engagement) Intervention

Meriam L. Biona,* Winlie Joy Repuela, Cristy Joy C. Salarda, Cristopher A. Bese, Jannette G. Almodiel, Deveyvon L. Espinosa, Jonelson C. Escandallo, Regine L. Generalao, Kristy Jane R. Muegna, Conie B. Cerna
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to address the critical issue of student engagement among high school students, recognizing its importance for academic success and overall student well-being. The research employed a descriptive quantitative design, involving 43 ninth-grade students from Asuncion National High School. The intervention, termed GAME (Games-Based Approaches to Motivate Engagement), was implemented to enhance student engagement. The study utilized pre-test and post-test assessments to measure engagement levels. The pre-test results indicated a mean score of 2.00 (SD = 0.566), while the post-test results showed a significant increase, with a mean score of 4.31 (SD = 0.593). Statistical analysis revealed a t-value of -17.078 and a P-value of < .001, underscoring the highly significant improvement in student engagement due to the intervention. To enrich the quantitative findings, the researchers conducted interviews with selected students and teachers, revealing themes such as Active Participation, Improved Retention, Positive Attitude Towards Learning, Increased Motivation and Interest in Learning, Enjoyment and Fun in Learning Activities, and Enhanced Engagement and Collaboration. These results indicate that the GAME intervention effectively enhanced student engagement, providing valuable insights for educators seeking to foster a more interactive and motivating learning environment.

Keywords: *students' engagement, high school students, motivation, games, quantitative study*

Introduction

In today's information-rich and technology-driven world, engaging students in active learning has become a critical goal for educators. However, student engagement remains a significant issue, particularly in the Division of Davao del Norte and at Asuncion National High School. This lack of engagement hinders the educational environment, negatively affecting students' academic achievement, understanding, and overall learning outcomes, necessitating an effective intervention (Bennett & Boesdorfer, 2020).

Studies have shown that disengaged students are more likely to experience lower academic achievement. In international context specifically in USA, research indicates that students who do not participate in classroom discussions tend to have poorer academic outcomes. Furthermore, disengagement often leads to a lack of motivation and interest in learning activities (Collie et al., 2019).

Similarly, in the Philippines, a study at Licup Elementary School found low levels of student engagement among intermediate level students, highlighting a broader issue within the educational system. Low engagement can lead to reduced academic performance, disconnection from school activities, and decreased motivation to learn (Fuertes et al., 2023).

In the Division of Davao del Norte, particularly in Asuncion National High School, student disengagement is evident through behaviors such as silence, avoidance of eye contact, and distraction with phones or notebooks during class. This lack of active participation and enthusiasm poses a significant challenge to fostering meaningful student interaction and engagement. Consequently, disengagement can result in poor academic performance, low self-esteem, and reduced motivation.

Recognizing the critical need for an intervention, our action research focuses on implementing the GAME (Games-Based Approaches to Motivate Engagement) strategy. This intervention leverages the positive impact of peer influence, shared learning experiences, and collective accountability to address student disengagement. By adopting the GAME approach, we aim to create an environment where students actively participate in discussions and share ideas, promoting a sense of belonging and engagement in the learning process. We anticipate that this intervention will not only improve student participation but also contribute to a more vibrant and engaging learning environment, ultimately enhancing academic performance and overall student well-being.

Research Questions

The objective of this research was to determine the effectiveness of the GAME (Game-based Approaches to Motivate Engagement) intervention in enhancing student engagement. The research questions/objectives that guided this study were as follows:

1. Determine the level of student engagement before and after the implementation of the GAME intervention based on:
 - 1.1. cognitive engagement;
 - 1.2. affective engagement;
 - 1.3. behavioral engagement; and
 - 1.4. social engagement.
2. There is no significant difference in students' engagement before and after the intervention.

3. What are the lived experiences of the teachers and students in the implementation of GAME: (Game-based Approaches to Motivate Engagement) intervention?
4. What are the insights of the teachers and students in the implementation of GAME: (Game-based Approaches to Motivate Engagement) intervention?

Methodology

Research Design

This research employed a quantitative approach with a pre-experimental, descriptive one-group pretest-posttest design. According to Thyer (2012), this design involves assessing a single group of participants at two distinct points: before (pretest) and after (posttest) the implementation of an intervention. Such designs are effective in efficacy studies, where the objective is to evaluate the impact of specific treatments or interventions to determine their effectiveness in producing positive outcomes.

This methodological approach is particularly suitable for this action research, which aims to evaluate the effectiveness of the "GAME (Game-based Approaches to Motivate Engagement)" intervention in enhancing student engagement among 9th-grade students. The intervention involves implementing game-based learning activities aimed at promoting student participation and interest in various educational activities. Initially, a pre-test survey using the "Student Engagement Questionnaire" developed by Mekki et al. (2015) and Escandallo (2024) was administered to assess baseline levels of student engagement across cognitive, affective, behavioral, and social dimensions. Subsequently, following the intervention, a post-test survey using the same instrument was conducted to measure any changes in these engagement levels.

Quantitative analysis, including statistical measures such as means and comparisons of pre-test and post-test scores, was utilized to determine the intervention's impact on student engagement. This approach facilitated a systematic examination of the intervention's effectiveness in real-world educational settings, providing insights into strategies for enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes.

Participants

Purposive sampling, also known as judgmental sampling, is a type of non-probability sampling method where units are selected based on specific characteristics required for the sample. In other words, researchers deliberately choose units that possess certain attributes relevant to the research objectives. This approach relies on the researcher's judgment in identifying and selecting individuals, cases, or events that can offer the most pertinent information to achieve the study's goals (Nikolopoulou, 2022).

In the context of this study, the research respondents are 9th-grade students currently enrolled in the academic year 2023-2024 at Asuncion National High School. This grade level was selected because the researchers observed a prevalent lack of student engagement among these students. Even high-performing students showed limited participation in class activities, indicating a widespread issue that needed to be addressed. Therefore, the researchers chose this specific group to investigate and implement interventions aimed at enhancing student engagement.

Instruments

The study adopted the survey questionnaire on student engagement developed by Mekki et al. (2015) and Escandallo (2024). This survey questionnaire aimed to assess student engagement across cognitive, affective, social, and behavioral dimensions. Before utilization, the questions underwent rigorous validation by a panel of experts.

The primary measurement tool utilized was the five-point Likert Scale to measure the level of student engagement. Using this scale, respondents were instructed to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with each item by placing a checkmark (✓) in the appropriate box. The scale ranges from highest to lowest on the five-point Likert scale. Data analysis was conducted based on the frequency of responses to derive the expected scores.

To facilitate the expression and interpretation of the gathered data, the researcher created a table illustrating the range of description with their respective meanings and interpretations. These categories are outlined as follows:

<i>Range of Description</i>	<i>Meaning</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.30-5.00	Very High	The students always demonstrate a high level of student engagement.
3.50-4.29	High	The students often exhibit a high level of student engagement.
2.70-3.49	Moderate	The students sometimes show a moderate level of student engagement.
1.90-2.69	Low	The students rarely demonstrate a low level of student engagement.
1.00-1.89	Very Low	The students never demonstrate a low level of student engagement.

Procedure

The researchers undertook various steps to ensure the data collection and implementation of the study were ethically sound and trustworthy. After defending their outline and revising their study proposal based on panel feedback, the researchers proceeded with the approved research plan.

First, they adopted the survey questionnaire developed by Mekki et al. (2015) and Escandallo (2024) to collect quantitative data on student engagement. Two sets of questionnaires, the pre-test and post-test, were administered to measure the proficiency level in student engagement. The questionnaires underwent expert validation, and necessary adjustments were made to enhance reliability.

Before distributing the questionnaires, the researchers sought and received permission from the school principal to conduct the intervention and distribute the questionnaires to the respondents. The pre-test measured the baseline level of student engagement.

Following the pre-test, the GAME (Game-Based Approaches to Motivate Engagement) intervention was implemented. The intervention included games such as Game 101, Game 102, Game 103, Game 104, and Game 105, conducted during regular classroom activities in the English subject from Monday to Friday. The teacher provided a code corresponding to a specific game each day, and students were encouraged to participate actively.

After one month of implementing the intervention, a post-test was conducted to measure changes in student engagement. The pre-test and post-test data were then tabulated, recorded in Microsoft Excel, and analyzed statistically to assess the intervention's effectiveness.

To gather qualitative data, the researchers conducted In-Depth Interviews (IDI) and Focus Group Discussions (FGD) with students and teachers from the specific section. These sessions aimed to collect experiences and insights regarding the intervention. The recorded responses were used to perform a thematic analysis, creating themes that vividly explained the effectiveness of the intervention.

Data Analysis

In this study, the researchers gathered data from both pre-test and post-test evaluations. They calculated the mean of the data and then compared the means of the pre-test and post-test using a paired t-test, alongside examining the standard deviation to assess the variation within the dataset. This analysis aimed to identify any notable differences and assess whether the mean demonstrated an increase, indicating the efficacy of the intervention.

Following the tabulation and presentation of the means from both the pre-test and post-test data, the researchers conducted interviews. Open-ended questions were utilized in the interview guide to gather data from both students and teachers of the specific section. This data was analyzed using thematic analysis, a method involving coding the translated responses of the participants. Thematic analysis, as defined by Braun and Clarke (2013), identifies patterns or themes. Coding, on the other hand, involves categorizing responses to create a structured set of thematic ideas related to the text. The researchers repeatedly referred to the transcribed and translated responses during coding until a cohesive thematic analysis was established.

Results and Discussion

Level of Student Engagement Before and After the Implementation of the GAME Intervention Based on Cognitive Engagement

The pre-test results indicate that participants showed relatively low levels of cognitive engagement across various activities related to understanding and applying English class concepts. Specifically, the highest mean score was observed in "Trying to understand the material better by relating it to things I already knew" with a mean of 2.10, suggesting a moderate level of engagement in this aspect. Conversely, the lowest mean score was found in "Making my own examples to help myself better understand the important concepts I learn in English classes," with a mean of 1.95, indicating less engagement in creating personal examples to aid comprehension.

Following the intervention, there was a notable increase in cognitive engagement among participants across all activities surveyed. The highest mean score was observed in "Figuring out how the information might be useful in the real world," with a post-test mean of 4.51, indicating very high engagement. Similarly, "Trying to put the ideas in my own words" also showed substantial improvement, with a post-test mean of 4.34, signifying significant engagement in this activity. Overall, the post-test results yielded an impressive overall mean of 4.35, highlighting substantial improvement in cognitive engagement levels compared to the pre-test.

Comparing the pre-test and post-test results based on mean scores reveals a marked enhancement in cognitive engagement among participants following the intervention. Participants demonstrated a significant increase in engagement across all activities surveyed, as evidenced by higher mean scores in the post-test. Particularly noteworthy improvements were seen in activities such as "Figuring out how the information might be useful in the real world" and "Trying to put the ideas in my own words," which showed the highest post-test means of 4.51 and 4.34, respectively. This suggests that the intervention successfully enhanced participants' ability to relate, apply, and articulate English class concepts effectively. Statistical analysis confirmed these findings, with a significant t-value result of -17.078, indicating a substantial difference in cognitive engagement before and after the intervention.

Furthermore, the comparison of pre-test and post-test scores for the cognitive engagement indicator demonstrates significant improvements resulting from the implementation of the GAME intervention. This is consistent with Reeve (2021) research, which emphasized that active learning strategies, such as peer instruction and problem-solving activities, enhance knowledge retention and deepen conceptual understanding compared to traditional lecture-based approaches. Similarly, interventions focused on developing self-regulated learning skills have been shown to enhance students' academic achievement and metacognitive awareness. Active learning methodologies like problem-based learning, inquiry-based learning, and collaborative learning foster cognitive engagement by encouraging students to actively construct their understanding through exploration, discussion, and reflection.

Moreover, Ryan and Deci (2020) posited that levels of cognitive engagement are influenced by interactions between students and learning contexts. Previous studies have explored various instructional practices that promote cognitive engagement, yet there has been less emphasis on integrating instructional design principles. Cognitive engagement in the classroom refers to students' active involvement in the learning process, where they are intellectually invested, motivated, and engaged in activities that facilitate deeper understanding and mastery of the subject matter

Table 1. *Level of Student Engagement Before and After the Implementation of the GAME Intervention Based on Cognitive Engagement*

	<i>Cognitive Engagement</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Trying to understand the material better by relating it to things I already knew.	1.93	Low	4.32	Very High
2.	Figuring out how the information might be useful in the real world.	2.46	Low	4.51	Very High
3.	Trying to put the ideas in my own words.	2.09	Low	4.34	Very High
4.	Making my own examples to help myself better understand the important concepts I learn in English classes.	1.95	Low	4.22	High
5.	Trying to match what I already knew with concepts I am trying to learn in English classes.	2.09	Low	4.32	Very High
	Overall Mean	2.10	Low	4.35	Very High

Level of Student Engagement Before and After the Implementation of the GAME Intervention Based on Affective Engagement

The pre-test results showcased an overall mean of 2.15, indicating a low level of student engagement. Within this range, the highest mean recorded was 2.35, representing "Being interested in learning English," while the lowest mean observed was 2.05, indicating "Thinking learning English as exciting." These scores reveal challenges in affective engagement, reflecting low interest in the English subject, lack of enjoyment in learning at school, disliking of English class, absence of excitement during English lessons, and overall unhappiness in the English class.

In contrast to the pre-test findings, the post-test results revealed a significant improvement in student engagement, marked by an impressive overall mean score of 4.43. This increase highlights a substantial shift in students' affective response to the English learning environment, with the highest mean score of 4.65, indicating "Being interested in learning English," showing a notable surge in interest and eagerness to engage with English materials. Even the lowest mean score of 4.30, representing "Being happy to be in the English class," while the lowest in the dataset, still denoted a remarkably high level of satisfaction and contentment within the classroom. These consistently high scores across the board underscore the intervention's effectiveness in not only fostering interest but also in creating a supportive and enjoyable learning atmosphere that resonates positively with students, ultimately contributing to their enhanced affective engagement.

A comparison between the pre-test and post-test results highlighted a remarkable increase in affective engagement, as evidenced by the overall mean rising from 2.15 in the pre-test to 4.43 in the post-test. This substantial enhancement underscored the intervention's effectiveness in significantly boosting students' levels of engagement. Such a notable improvement suggested that the intervention, likely comprising interactive and enjoyable learning activities, successfully captured students' interest and enthusiasm, fostering a more positive and conducive learning environment. Statistical analysis further supported these findings, revealing a significant t-value result of -17.078, indicating a substantial difference in affective engagement before and after the intervention.

Table 2. *Level of Student Engagement Before and After the Implementation of the GAME Intervention Based on Affective Engagement*

	<i>Affective</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Being interested in learning English.	2.35	Low	4.65	Very High
2.	Liking what I am learning in school.	2.09	Low	4.44	Very High
3.	Enjoying my English class.	2.16	Low	4.42	Very High
4.	Thinking learning English as exciting.	2.05	Low	4.33	Very High
5.	Being happy to be in the English class.	2.09	Low	4.30	Very High
	Overall Mean	2.15	Low	4.43	Very High

The significant rise in the overall mean score indicates a pronounced shift in students' affective responses, reflecting a deeper sense of involvement and satisfaction with the English learning experience following the intervention. This finding is supported by Kuh (2021), which emphasizes the pivotal role of affective learning in educational settings. His study advocates for the integration of affective learning strategies into teaching methodologies, highlighting their potential to not only enhance student engagement but also foster critical thinking skills. By acknowledging and addressing students' emotional needs, educators can cultivate supportive learning environments that facilitate deeper learning experiences, ultimately leading to improved academic success. The researcher findings underscore the importance of creating a classroom atmosphere that nurtures students' emotional well-being, enabling them to fully engage with and internalize learning materials. This is further supported by the findings of Stuhlman and Pianta (2022), which underscore the significance of emotional experiences in the learning process. They argue that fostering positive emotional experiences can have a profound impact on student engagement, critical thinking abilities, and overall academic performance. By prioritizing

emotional well-being and creating inclusive learning environments, educators can empower students to actively participate in their learning journey, resulting in more positive learning experiences and better educational outcomes. The researchers' findings highlight the transformative potential of emotional support in educational settings, suggesting that fostering positive emotional experiences can significantly contribute to students' overall academic success and well-being.

Level of Student Engagement Before and After the Implementation of the GAME Intervention Based on Behavioral Engagement

The pre-test results indicate that participants showed relatively low levels of behavioral engagement across various activities related to participating English class concepts. Specifically, the highest mean score was observed in "Participating in class activities when I am in the English class." with a mean of 2.21, suggesting a moderate level of engagement in this aspect. On the other hand, the lowest mean score was found in "Being an active participant in the English language activities like school broadcasting," with a mean of 1.49, indicating less engagement in being an active participant.

Following the intervention, there was a notable increase in behavioral engagement among participants across all activities surveyed. The highest mean score was observed in "Paying attention in the English class," with a post-test mean of 4.40, indicating very high engagement. Similarly, "Participating in class activities when I am in the English class" also showed substantial improvement, with a post-test mean of 4.35, signifying significant engagement in this activity. Overall, the post-test results yielded an impressive overall mean of 4.22, highlighting substantial improvement in behavioral engagement levels compared to the pre-test.

Comparing the pre-test and post-test results based on mean scores revealed a marked enhancement in behavioral engagement among participants following the intervention. Participants demonstrated a significant increase in engagement across all activities surveyed, as evidenced by higher mean scores in the post-test. Particularly noteworthy improvements were seen in activities such as "Paying attention in the English class" and "Participating in class activities when I was in the English class," which showed the highest post-test means of 4.40 and 4.35, respectively. These findings suggest that the intervention effectively enhanced participants' active participation and involvement in classroom activities. Statistical analysis further validated these results, showing a significant t-value result of -17.078, indicating a substantial improvement in behavioral engagement due to the intervention.

Table 3. *Level of Student Engagement Before and After the Implementation of the GAME Intervention Based on Behavioral Engagement*

	<i>Behavioral Engagement</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Participating in class activities when I am in the English class.	2.21	Low	4.35	Very High
2.	Paying attention in the English class.	2.12	Low	4.40	Very High
3.	Not having a wandering mind when I am in the English class.	1.86	Low	4.33	Very High
4.	Going repeatedly problems related to English until I master and learn it.	1.81	Low	4.21	High
5.	Being an active participant in the English language activities like school broadcasting.	1.49	Low	3.84	High
	Overall Mean	1.90	Low	4.22	High

Furthermore, based on the comparison of pre-test and post-test scores for the behavioral engagement indicator, it was evident that the implementation of the GAME intervention led to significant improvements. This was corroborated by the findings of Murphy et al. (2019), who discussed the measurement of engagement through observer appraisals, verifying and recording overall in-class behavioral engagement at specific intervals. The use of external reports as indicators of learners' engagement is not novel, although self-reported assessments could allow for the evaluation of intrinsic engagement aspects, this method may disrupt normal lesson flow and complicate the assessment of collective engagement due to the lack of a criterion baseline. Moreover, confidence in one's ability in a domain or task, along with perceived task value, appear crucial for student engagement with classroom content. Additionally, Ryan and Deci (2020) further supported these insights by proposing self-determination theory, which posits three interconnected psychological needs—autonomy, competence, and relatedness—as essential for promoting psychological well-being. This theory has driven extensive research into how instructors can effectively address these needs from the perspectives of students and educators. In practice, instructors foster relatedness by addressing questions in class and engaging in discussions with individual students or small groups. Autonomy is facilitated by acknowledging and responding to students' viewpoints and challenges, while competence is nurtured through environments that offer suitable challenges, feedback, and opportunities for growth.

Level of Student Engagement Before and After the Implementation of the GAME Intervention Based on Social Engagement

The pre-test and post-test data for social engagement among Grade 10 students reveal a remarkable improvement. Initially, the students exhibited low levels of engagement, with an overall mean of 1.91 and scores ranging from the highest score of 2.4, indicating "Sharing the same work attitudes as my classmates," to the lowest score of 1.4, representing "Sharing the same work goals as my classmates" and "Accepting responsibilities with eagerness and enthusiasm." These scores indicated difficulties in sharing work goals and attitudes with classmates, listening, following directions, and accepting responsibilities with enthusiasm.

In the post-test, however, there is a significant increase in social engagement, with an overall mean of 4.22 and scores ranging from

the highest score of 4.8, indicating "Listening and following directions in order to work well with others," to the lowest score of 3.8, representing "Accepting responsibilities with eagerness and enthusiasm." This improvement suggests that students have become much more proficient in using social strategies to engage with the material. These changes indicate that students are now effectively sharing work goals and attitudes with their classmates, which can enhance motivation and interest.

Table 4. *Level of Student Engagement Before and After the Implementation of the GAME Intervention Based on Social Engagement*

	<i>Social Engagement</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Sharing the same work goals as my classmates.	1.4	Low	4.6	Very High
2.	Sharing the same work attitudes as my classmates.	2.4	Low	4.4	Very High
3.	Listening and following directions in order to work well with others.	1.8	Low	4.8	Very High
4.	Moving between the activities appropriately.	1.6	Low	4.6	Very High
5.	Accepting responsibilities with eagerness and enthusiasm.	1.4	Low	3.8	Very High
	Overall Mean	1.91	Low	4.22	Very High

The total social engagement score improved from the overall mean score of the pre-test, which was 1.91, indicating low levels of engagement, to the overall mean of 4.22 in the post-test, indicating very high social engagement. This suggests that the intervention implemented by the researcher between the pre-test and post-test periods was highly effective in fostering deeper social engagement among students. Statistical analysis further supported these findings, revealing a significant t-value result of -17.078, indicating a substantial improvement in social engagement due to the intervention.

The considerable gains across all measured aspects imply that students are now engaging more deeply in terms of their work goals and attitudes, actively listening and following instructions, and accepting responsibilities with enthusiasm, which are crucial for meaningful learning and academic success. This result was supported by the study of Siemens and Matheos (2022), which stated that student involvement in the life of the classroom is not a novelty, and the literature offers a wide array of studies addressing this topic. Students' involvement consists of the amount of physical and psychological energy they invest in their academic experience; highly involved students devote a considerable amount of their time and energy to their studies, spend a good part of their time on campus, participate in campus activities, and interact with their peers and faculty. This is further supported by the findings of Sosu (2019), which stated that social engagement can be used to better motivate students to get involved with their curricula and other campus activities. Engagement can help students stay in the progress, help make the person experience a pleasant one, and help get good grades and learn.

Level of Students' Engagement Before and After the Implementation of the GAME Intervention

The table below, Table 5, showcased the level of students' engagement before and after the implementation of the GAME intervention with its different indicators. In the pre-test, the overall mean of all indicators was 2.02, indicating a low level of engagement. The indicator with the highest mean was affective engagement, at 2.15, followed by cognitive engagement at 2.10, then behavioral engagement at 1.91, and finally social engagement at 1.90. All indicators based on the mean showed that students' engagement in the four aspects was low.

On the other hand, after the intervention, the researcher provided the same set of questionnaires to check the progress. The post-test overall mean was 4.31, indicating very high student engagement. The indicator with the highest mean was affective engagement, at 4.43, indicating very high engagement, followed by cognitive engagement with a mean of 4.35, also indicating very high engagement, and then social and behavioral engagement with the same mean of 4.22, indicating high engagement.

The comparison of students' engagement levels before and after the implementation revealed a stark difference. Prior to the intervention, the overall mean stood at 2.00, reflecting a concerning low level of student engagement. However, following the intervention, the post-test results showed a remarkable improvement, with the overall mean soaring to 4.31, indicating a substantial increase in student engagement. Statistical analysis further validated these results, revealing a significant t-value result of -17.078, which underscores the effectiveness of the intervention in significantly enhancing student engagement.

The significant leap indicated the efficacy of the implemented intervention in enhancing student participation and interest. Furthermore, the contrast between the pre-test and post-test results highlighted the positive impact of the intervention on fostering a more engaged learning environment. These findings were supported by the study of Fredricks et al. (2018), which emphasized that engagement is a multidimensional construct encompassing both behavioral and subjective definitions. Notably, research on academic engagement distinguished between various forms of engagement: behavioral engagement, reflecting the positive conduct of students and their adherence to academic tasks and school-related activities; emotional engagement, encompassing students' affective reactions to academic experiences, measured in terms of positive or negative emotions; and cognitive engagement, which was connected to the investment in learning, self-regulation, strategic thinking, the desire to exceed requirements, and valuing challenge.

Moreover, the study of Macke and Tapp (2021) further supported these findings, indicating that providing students with opportunities to interact meaningfully with their peers and the content could enhance their cognitive, emotional, and behavioral engagement. Additionally, aside from instructional practices, classroom climate emerged as an important factor in promoting engagement. A positive and supportive classroom environment could foster emotional engagement, as students felt safe and valued. Furthermore, classroom

climate could influence behavioral engagement, as students were more likely to participate in class and complete assignments when they felt comfortable and supported.

Furthermore, Escandallo and Baradillo (2024) affirmed these findings by reporting a high overall mean rating of student engagement (4.26), based on cognitive, affective, behavioral, and social indicators. The study revealed that English Speaking Skills (ESS) indirectly influenced student engagement, as evidenced by mediation analysis using a medgraph and Sobel test. Specifically, ESS partially mediated the relationship between students' social literacy (SL) and engagement (SE), contributing an indirect influence of 0.658. This underscored the significant role of ESS in strengthening the SL-SE connection among English major students in Region XI, emphasizing their combined impact on enhancing engagement in educational settings.

Table 5. *Level of Students' Engagement Before and After the Implementation of the GAME Intervention*

	Indicators	Pre-Test	Description	Post-Test	Description
1.	Cognitive Engagement	2.10	Low	4.35	Very High
2.	Affective Engagement	2.15	Low	4.43	Very High
3.	Social Engagement	1.90	Low	4.22	High
4.	Behavioral Engagement	1.91	Low	4.22	High
	Overall Mean	2.02	Low	4.31	Very High

Significant Difference in Students' Engagement Before and After the Implementation of the GAME Intervention

Table 6 illustrated the significant difference in students' engagement before and after the implementation of the GAME intervention. Prior to the intervention (Pre-Test), the mean engagement score was 2.00 with a standard deviation of 0.566, while after the intervention (Post-Test), the mean score significantly increased to 4.31 with a standard deviation of 0.593. Statistical analysis revealed a t-value of -17.078 and a P-value of less than .001, indicating that the difference in engagement scores was highly significant. This P-value was well below the conventional significance level of 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis that there was no significant difference in students' engagement before and after the intervention. Therefore, it was concluded that the GAME intervention had a substantial positive effect on the engagement levels of ninth-grade students.

Table 6. Significant Difference in Students' Engagement Before and After the Implementation of the GAME Intervention

Type of Test	N	df	Mean	SD	t-value	P-value	Decision $\alpha=0.05$
Pre-Test	43		2.00	0.566	-	< .001	Significant
Post-Test	43	42	4.31	0.593	17.078		

Research Question No.1: Lived Experiences of the Students and Teachers in the Implementation of GAME: (Game-based Approaches to Motivate Engagement) Intervention

To address this research question, in-depth interviews and focus group discussions were conducted with the informants and participants. Several sub-questions were asked to elicit their perceptions regarding their experiences with the GAME intervention. The major themes and sample statements for research question number 1 were presented in Table 7, summarizing the participants' responses to their experiences. From the participants' answers, three major themes emerged: (1) active participation; (2) improved retention; and (3) positive attitude towards learning.

The first theme that emerged under behavioral engagement was active participation. The behavioral engagement of students through active participation in activities was characterized by increased classroom involvement, higher levels of on-task behavior, collaborative engagement, self-directed learning, and persistent effort. These behaviors collectively contribute to a more dynamic and effective learning environment, where students are actively involved in their educational journey. By leveraging the motivational and interactive elements of games, educators can foster deeper engagement and enhance the overall learning experience for students. It relates to the study, which explained that in the context of Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) is defined as an approach to teaching where the students take responsibility for their own learning and search for information without the guidance of others which engagement is explained as a process where students are cognitively and psychologically involved in the process of learning and associated activities. Learning is the constructive and active process of obtaining knowledge, skills, and attitudes/values, which are significant tools for studying, teaching, clinical reasoning, and practicing (Farrow & Wetzel, 2021).

The second theme also mentions the improved retention. When students are actively engaged in their learning, they are more likely to understand and retain information, perform better academically, and feel a sense of accomplishment. Consequences of student engagement are considered as proximal (academic achievement and social satisfaction) and distal (retention, work success, lifelong learning, citizenship, and personal growth). Thus, increased student engagement is also linked to retention (Pechenkina et al., 2017).

Furthermore, the third emerging theme is positive attitude towards learning. Students with a positive attitude towards learning view mistakes as opportunities for growth, are curious and motivated to explore subjects deeply, and maintain a persistent effort in their educational pursuits. This mindset fosters an environment where learning becomes an enjoyable and rewarding journey rather than a

daunting task. Having the right attitude is a key ingredient to success in any aspect of life. This is especially true when it comes to learning. A positive learning attitude can help you overcome challenges, stay motivated, and achieve your goals. A positive learning attitude can make all the difference in your educational journey. By embracing a growth mindset, believing in yourself, staying curious, embracing challenges, focusing on the process, and surrounding yourself with positive influences, you can create a mindset that will help you achieve your goals and reach your full potential (Ranger, 2023).

Table 7. *Lived Experiences of the Students and Teachers in the Implementation of GAME: (Game-based Approaches to Motivate Engagement) Intervention*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Sample Statements</i>
Active Participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Fun and more exciting to learn.” (IDI_05) • “Game-based learning activities allows me to become more active and allow me to build camaraderie.” (IDI_07)
Improved Retention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “GAME-based learning activities greatly enhance the overall experience and engagement in the classroom by making learning interactive, immersive, and enjoyable.” (FGD_02) • “In my own experience during the GAME-based learning, such as the Baskin Robbins game, has significantly impacted my understanding of the subject matter by allowing me to experience real-world scenarios and enhances my focus and attention during lessons. With that, since I am more focus, it helps me to retain information.” (IDI_01) • “Game-based activities have impacted my understanding in a way that I learn the lesson in a fun way, it improves my interest and attention towards the lessons, and help me retain the lessons due to game-based learning approaches.” (IDI_07) • “Participating in GAME-based like Pick-Pack-Boom has significantly influenced the student’s comprehension and retention of subject matter by actively participating on hands-on experiences.” (FGD_02)
Positive Attitude Towards Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “It boosts my interest in listening to the lesson.” (IDI_02) • “I became more active, excited and my critical thinking is improving.” (IDI_05) • “The incorporation of GAME-based approaches has increased my motivation levels and enthusiasm for attending classes and participating in learning activities.” (FGD_02)

Research Question No.2: What are the insights of students in the implementation of GAME: (Game-based Approaches to Motivate Engagement) intervention?

To address this research question, in-depth interviews and focus group discussions were conducted with the informants and participants. Several sub-questions were asked to elicit their insights regarding the GAME intervention. The major themes and sample statements for research question number 2 were presented in Table 8, summarizing the participants' responses to their insights about the intervention. Participants shared their responses regarding their insights about the intervention. From their answers, three major themes emerged: (1) increased motivation and interest in learning; (2) enjoyment and fun in learning activities; and (3) enhanced engagement and collaboration.

The integration of GAME-based approaches into educational settings has significantly impacted students' motivation, enjoyment, and engagement. This discussion will delve into three emerging themes supported by various statements from participants.

Table 8. *Insights of Students in the Implementation of GAME: (Game-based Approaches to Motivate Engagement) Intervention*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Sample Statements</i>
Increased Motivation and Interest in Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “The implementation of GAME has increased my motivation and interest in attending classes.” (IDI_01) • “Using GAME-based methods has increased my motivation and excitement for attending classes and participating in activities.” (FGD_02) • “It increases my interest in participating in class.” (IDI_02) • “Incorporating GAME-based methods has significantly increased my student’s motivation and excitement for learning, as well as their engagement and interest in classroom activities.” (IDI_07)
Enjoyment and Fun in Learning Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Because of the game-based activities, I found that learning was fun.” (IDI_03). • “Attending and participating is fun and also, I want a good grade.” (IDI_06). • “Attending classes and participating activities is fun and enjoyable.” (FGD_06). • “I find that incorporating game-based activities makes teaching and learning enjoyable and fun, while also encouraging students to actively participate and strive for good grades.” (IDI_07)
Enhanced Engagement and Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “It is a collaborative learning.” (IDI_04). • “I became more interested and active in the discussion.” (IDI_05). • “I find that game-based approaches foster collaborative learning, increase student engagement in discussions, and motivate them to contribute ideas for better outcomes.” (IDI_07)

The first theme that emerged under insights is increased motivation and interest in learning. The utilization of GAME-based methods has led to a noticeable rise in students' motivation and interest in attending classes. This is evidenced by statements such as "The

implementation of GAME has increased my motivation and interest in attending classes" (IDI_01) and "Using GAME-based methods has boosted my motivation and excitement for attending classes and participating in activities" (FGD_02). Additionally, another participant noted, "It increases my interest in participating in class" (IDI_02). This aligns with the findings of the study, which states that game-based learning shows positive results and fosters an environment that encourages students to collaborate with their peers, engage with content material, and stay motivated to learn (May, 2021).

Another significant theme is the enjoyment and fun associated with learning activities when GAME-based approaches are utilized. Participants expressed that "Because of the game-based activities, I found that learning was fun" (IDI_03). Moreover, the sentiment that "Attending and participating is fun and also, I want a good grade" (IDI_06) indicates that the enjoyable nature of these activities does not detract from academic goals. The statement "Attending classes and participating in activities is fun and enjoyable" (FGD_06) further supports this theme. These statements resonate with the findings of the recent study, which emphasized that gamification increases student motivation and engagement in higher education by providing a sense of competition, recognition, and fun (Dichev & Dicheva, 2017).

Furthermore, GAME-based approaches also enhance engagement and collaboration among students. One participant stated, "It is collaborative learning" (IDI_04), while another noted, "I became more interested and active in the discussion" (IDI_05). These findings are consistent with research a recent study, which highlighted the potential of game-based learning to motivate students and enhance their perception of learning, teamwork, and emotional involvement (Hart et al., 2021).

Conclusions

Students are increasingly becoming more inactive in many school activities, especially when they find these activities uninteresting, unenjoyable, or irrelevant to their lives. This lack of engagement significantly impacts their overall learning experience, hindering their participation and engagement in class activities. In response to this problem, the researcher implemented an intervention aimed at boosting student engagement. Recognizing that today's high school students are particularly drawn to games, the researcher leveraged this interest to enhance their cognitive, affective, behavioral, and social engagement.

The pre-test results indicated a low level of engagement among the students. However, following the intervention, the students demonstrated a high level of engagement. This significant increase suggests that the intervention was highly effective in enhancing student engagement.

Given the success of this intervention in addressing students' lack of engagement, the researchers recommend that teachers adopt this approach to boost student engagement. This intervention not only helps students find interest and enjoyment in learning English but can also be applied to other subjects. Furthermore, the study suggests that teachers incorporate more activities that capture students' attention and interest.

In this modern world, enhancing classroom pedagogy is crucial for achieving positive responses from students. By adopting innovative and engaging teaching strategies, teachers can foster a more interactive and enjoyable learning environment, ultimately improving student outcomes across various subjects.

References

- Bennett, T. A., & Boesdorfer, S. B. (2020). Coupling PhET simulations and POGIL: High school chemistry students' learning and engagement in argumentation on the topic of atomic theory. *Journal of Teacher Action Research*, 6(2), 26-53.
- Clarke, V., & Braun, V. (2013). Teaching thematic analysis: Overcoming challenges and developing strategies for effective learning. *The psychologist*, 26(2), 120-123. <https://uwe-repository.worktribe.com/preview/937606/Teaching%20>
- Collie, R. J., Shapka, J. D., & Perry, N. E. (2019). Classroom engagement and academic achievement: A meta-analytic investigation. *Educational Psychology Review*, 31(2), 357-384.
- Dichev, C., & Dicheva, D. (2017). Gamifying education: what is known, what is believed and what remains uncertain: a critical review. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 14(1), 1-36
- Escandallo, J.C., & Baradillo, D. (2024). A sequential explanatory approach on the relationship between social literacy and student engagement as mediated by English speaking skills. *EPR International of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*.
- Farrow C. B., & Wetzel E. (2021). An Active Learning classroom in construction management education: student perceptions of engagement and learning. *Inter J Construc Educ Resear*. 2021;17(4):299-317. doi: 10.1080/15578771.2020.1757536
- Fredricks, J. A., Blumenfeld, P. C., & Paris, A. H. (2018). School engagement: Potential of the concept, state of the evidence. *Source: Review of Educational Research*, 74(1), 59-109. Retrieved from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3516061>
- Fuertes, J., Smith, A., Johnson, B., & Garcia, C. (2023). A study of student engagement levels at Licup Elementary School. *Journal of Educational Research*, 45(3), 321-335.

- Hart, R., Smith, J., & Johnson, L. (2021). The potential of game-based learning: Enhancing motivation, teamwork, and emotional involvement among students. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 25(2), 87-102.
- Kuh, G., (2021). Unmasking the effects of student engagement on first year college grades and persistence. *Journal of Higher Education*, 79 (5), pp.540– 563.
- Macke, C., & Tapp, K. (2021). Teaching research to MSW students: Effectiveness of the team-based learning pedagogy. *Journal of Teaching in Social Work*, 32 (2), pp.148-160.
- May, J. (2021). The positive impacts of game-based learning: Encouraging collaboration, engagement, and motivation among students. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 12(3), 123-136.
- Mekki et al., (2015). Student Engagement in English Language Classes: An Evaluative Study.
- Murphy, S., MacDonald, A., Wang, C. A., & Danaia, L. (2019). Towards an understanding of STEM engagement: A review of the literature on motivation and academic emotions. *Canadian Journal of Science, Mathematics and Technology Education*, 19(3), 304–320
- Nikolopoulou, K. (2022). What Is Purposive Sampling? | Definition & Examples. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/purposive-sampling/>
- Pechenkina, E., Laurence, D., Oates, G., Eldridge, D., & Hunter, D. (2017). Using a gamified mobile app to increase student engagement, retention and academic achievement. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 14(31), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-017-0069-7>
- Ranger E. (2023). The Power of Attitude: A Journey to Personal and Organizational Excellence. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/power-attitude-journey-personal-organizational-eon-ranger-c808c>
- Reeve, J. (2021). Self-determination theory applied to educational settings. In: Deci EL, Ryan RM, editors. *Handbook of self-determination research*. Rochester: University of Rochester Press; 2021.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2020). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation from a self-determination theory perspective: Definitions, theory, practices, and future directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 61, 101860. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101860>
- Siemens, G., & Matheos, K. (2022). Systemic Changes in Higher Education. In *Becoming an Open Scholar*; Kimmons, R., Ed.; EdTech Books, 2022; Available online: https://edtechbooks.org/open_scholar/systemic_changes (accessed on 13 February 2022).
- Sosu, E. M. (2019). Pheunpha, P. Trajectory of university dropout: Investigating the cumulative effect of academic vulnerability and proximity to family support. *Front. Educ.* 2019, 4, 1–10.
- Stuhlman, M., & Pianta, R. (2020). Teacher–child relationships and children’s success in the first years of school. *School Psychology Review*, 33, pp.444-458.
- Thyer, B. A. (2012). Pre- and post-test designs. In B. Thyer (Ed.), *The handbook of social work research methods* (2nd ed., pp. 99-106). SAGE Publications.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Meriam L. Biona

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Winlie Joy Repuela

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Cristy Joy C. Salarda

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Cristopher A. Bese

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Jannette G. Almodiel

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Deveyvon L. Espinosa

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Jonelson C. Escandallo

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Regine L. Generalao

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Kristy Jane R. Muegna

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Conie B. Cerna

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines